

Sums over Partitions into Distinct Parts

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Abstract— In this paper, we are going to present sums over partitions. We define a function $u_n(g; q)$, which can be considered as one generalization of q -Pochhammer symbol. Using this function $u_n(g; q)$, many results have been proved for sums of partitions into even distinct parts, odd distinct parts, 1 as the only part and $v = v$ as a part.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Definition 1.1. Riemann zeta function is defined by the convergent series

$$\zeta(\kappa) = \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} v^{-\kappa} = \frac{1}{1^\kappa} + \frac{1}{2^\kappa} + \frac{1}{3^\kappa} + \cdots + \frac{1}{v^\kappa} + \cdots \quad \text{Re } \kappa > 1. \quad (1.1)$$

Initially, Euler [3] gave the product formula of the zeta function for the real variable, but Riemann [6] viewed zeta function as a function of a complex variable. One of its applications is that it connects complex analysis to number theory. Recently, Singh [8] discussed the values of the Riemann zeta function for integers.

The number theoretic properties are inherent in $\zeta(\kappa)$. These are given by the following formulae

$$\zeta(\kappa) = \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{v^\kappa} = \prod_{p_v} (1 - p_v^{-\kappa})^{-1} \quad (1.2)$$

where the product is taken over all prime numbers $p_v = 2, 3, 5, 7, \dots$.

Definition 1.2. A positive integer v can be written as a sum of positive integers as,

$$v = v_1 + v_2 + \cdots + v_k$$

with $v_1 \geq v_2 \geq \cdots \geq v_k$ (and $k \geq 1$), then the number of ways to write the sum of above form of a positive integer is called the partition function and denoted by $p(v)$. We call the integers v_j 's as the parts of the partition. It's not necessary for the parts to be distinct, and two partitions are same if they differ only in the order of their parts. Consider $p(0)=1$.

For examples

$$3 = 3 = 2 + 1 = 1 + 1 + 1, \quad p(3) = 3.$$

$$4 = 4 = 3 + 1 = 2 + 2 = 2 + 1 + 1 = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1, \quad p(4) = 5.$$

Euler [3] discovered the generating function for the partition function which is given as

$$\sum_{v=0}^{\infty} p(v)q^v = \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^v)^{-1} = \frac{1}{(q; q)_{\infty}} \tag{1.3}$$

Here, in keeping with the spirit of Euler, we take on the following kind of sum over partitions

$$\sum_{\mu \in \mathcal{P}} g(\mu).$$

Sums of the above form carry out many fascinating transformations and often reveal some special patterns with sums over natural numbers. In 2016, Schneider [7] established partition-theoretic formulas using q series, infinite products, and sums over integer partitions. He made connections between sums over partitions and many number-theoretic concepts, including the Riemann zeta function and multiple zeta values. In Section 3, we define a function $u_n(g; q)$, which can be considered as one generalization of the q -Pochhammer symbol. By using this function $u_n(g; q)$, two theorems have been proved that result in a sum over partitions into even distinct parts. While in Section 4, three theorems have been proved by considering sum over partitions as odd distinct parts, 1 as the only part, and $v = v$ as a part.

2. NOTATIONS

For $|q| < 1$, the following q notations are used:

$$(\omega; q)_n = (1 - \omega)(1 - \omega q)(1 - \omega q^2) \cdots (1 - \omega q^n), \quad (\omega; q)_0 = 1. \tag{2.1}$$

$$(\omega; q)_{\infty} = (1 - \omega)(1 - \omega q)(1 - \omega q^2) \cdots . \tag{2.2}$$

$$(q; q)_n = (1 - q)(1 - q^2)(1 - q^3) \cdots (1 - q^n). \tag{2.3}$$

$$(q; q)_{\infty} = (1 - q)(1 - q^2)(1 - q^3) \cdots \tag{2.4}$$

The infinite series of the form

$$1 + q + q^2 + q^3 + \cdots = (1 - q)^{-1} \tag{2.5}$$

is convergent for $|q| < 1$.

We also used the following notations and terminology:

If $\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_r$ are the integer parts of a partition μ , then

- The number of parts of μ is r . It is called the **length of partition** and denoted by $l(\mu)$, so $l(\mu) = r$.
- Sum of all the parts is called **size** or **weight of the partition**, and denote by $|\mu|$, i.e., $|\mu| = \mu_1 + \mu_2 + \cdots + \mu_r$. Also, μ is a partition of v is denoted by $\mu \vdash v$, and $|\mu| = v$.
- The product of parts of μ is called the **integer** of μ , and denoted by v_{μ} , i.e., $v_{\mu} = \mu_1 \mu_2 \cdots \mu_r$. Conventionally, $l(\emptyset) = 0$, $|\emptyset| = 0$, and $v_{\emptyset} = 1$.

3. SUMS OVER PARTITIONS AS EVEN DISTINCT PARTS

Before stating the theorems for sums over partitions as even distinct parts, we have to define $u_n(g; q)$.

For a function $g : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, we define $u_n(g; q)$ as

$$u_n(g; q) = \prod_{v=1}^n (1 - g(v)q^v), \quad n \geq 1, \quad u_0(g; q) = 1. \tag{3.1}$$

If the product $\prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(v)q^v)$ converges, then

$$u_{\infty}(g; q) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n(g; q).$$

Hence, u can be considered as a generalization of q -Pochhammer symbol. Setting $g =$ a constant w , we get

$$u_n(w; q) = (wq; q)_n, \quad u_{\infty}(w; q) = (wq; q)_{\infty}.$$

In particular, if $g(v) = 1$, then (3.1) reduces to (2.3).

Thus,

$$u_{e,\infty}(g; q) = \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v)q^{2v}),$$

and

$$u_{o,\infty}(g; q) = \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v - 1)q^{2v-1}).$$

Since $1/u_{\infty}(g; q) = \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(v)q^v)^{-1}$ is of the form of

(i) the product $\prod_{p_v} (1 - p_v^{-\kappa})^{-1}$ as in (1.2), and

(ii) the product $\prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^v)^{-1}$ in (1.3),

so it creates interest us.

Theorem 3.1. *If the product*

$$\frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} = \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v)q^{2v})^{-1}$$

converges, then there are other equivalent forms of it, viz.

- (i) $\frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} = \sum_{\mu \in P^e} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i)$
- (ii) $\frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} = 1 + \Lambda$ where $\Lambda = \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \frac{q^{2v} g(2v)}{u_{e,2v}(g; q)}$
- (iii) $\frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} = 1 + \frac{T}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)}$ where $T = \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} q^{2v} g(2v) u_{e,2v-2}(g; q)$
- (iv) $\frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} = 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^v q^{(-1)v(v-1)}}{u_{e,v}(\frac{1}{g}; q^{-1}) \prod_{k=1}^{v-1} g(2k)}$
- (v) $\frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} = 1 + \frac{T}{1 - \frac{\Lambda}{1 + \frac{T}{1 - \frac{\Lambda}{1 + \dots}}}}$

where P^e be the set of partitions into even distinct parts.

Proof Let P^e be the set of partitions into even distinct parts . Since $l(\emptyset) = 0$, $v_\emptyset = 1$, and considering the even distinct parts of partitions, so we notice that

$$\begin{aligned} 2 &= 2, & 4 &= 4, & 6 &= 6, & 4 + 2, \\ 8 &= 8, & 6 + 2, & 10 &= 10, & 8 + 2, & 6 + 4, \dots \end{aligned}$$

(i) By definition of $u_{e,\infty}(g; q)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} &= \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v)q^{2v})^{-1} \\ &= (1 - g(2)q^2)^{-1}(1 - g(4)q^4)^{-1}(1 - g(6)q^6)^{-1}(1 - g(8)q^8)^{-1}(1 - g(10)q^{10})^{-1} \dots \\ &= (1 + g(2)q^2 + g(2)^2q^{2+2} + g(2)^3q^{2+2+2} + g(2)^4q^{2+2+2+2} + \dots) \\ &\quad (1 + g(4)q^4 + g(4)^2q^{4+4} + \dots) \\ &\quad (1 + g(6)q^6 + g(6)^2q^{6+6} + \dots) \\ &\quad (1 + g(8)q^8 + \dots) \dots \\ &= 1 + g(2)q^2 + (g(2)^2q^{2+2} + g(4)q^4) + (g(2)^3q^{2+2+2} + g(2)g(4)q^{2+4} + g(6)q^6) \\ &\quad + (g(2)^4q^{2+2+2+2} + g(2)g(2)g(4)q^{2+2+4} + g(4)^2q^{4+4} + g(2)g(6)q^{2+6} + g(8)q^8) + \dots \\ &= 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} q^{2v} \sum_{\mu \vdash 2v} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) \\ &= \sum_{\mu \in P^e} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) \end{aligned}$$

(ii) Next,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} &= \frac{1}{u_{e,0}(g; q)} + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{u_{e,2v}(g; q)} - \frac{1}{u_{e,2v-2}(g; q)} \right] \\ &= 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{\prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v)q^{2v})} - \frac{1}{\prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v-2)q^{2v-2})} \right] \\ &= 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v-2)q^{2v-2})} \left[\frac{1}{1 - g(2v)q^{2v}} - 1 \right] \\ &= 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{u_{e,2v-2}(g; q)} \left[\frac{1}{1 - g(2v)q^{2v}} - 1 \right] \\ &= 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \frac{q^{2v}g(2v)}{u_{e,2v}(g; q)} \\ &= 1 + \Lambda \quad \text{where} \quad \Lambda = \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \frac{q^{2v}g(2v)}{u_{e,2v}(g; q)} \end{aligned}$$

(iii) Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{e,\infty}(g; q) &= u_{e,0}(g; q) + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} (u_{e,2v}(g; q) - u_{e,2v-2}(g; q)) \\
 &= 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \left[\prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v)q^{2v}) - \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v-2)q^{2v-2}) \right] \\
 &= 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \left[\prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v-2)q^{2v-2}) (1 - g(2v)q^{2v} - 1) \right] \\
 &= 1 - \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} q^{2v} g(2v) u_{e,2v-2}(g; q)
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$u_{e,\infty}(g; q) = 1 - T \quad \text{where} \quad T = \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} q^{2v} g(2v) u_{e,2v-2}(g; q). \tag{3.2}$$

From Theorem 3.1 (ii), we have

$$\Lambda = \frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} - 1 = \frac{1 - u_{e,\infty}(g; q)}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)}$$

Using (3.2), we get

$$\Lambda = \frac{T}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)}. \tag{3.3}$$

Theorem 3.1 (ii) and the above expression give Theorem 3.1 (iii).

(iv) Consider

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{e,v} \left(\frac{1}{g}; \frac{1}{q} \right) &= \prod_{k=1}^v \left[1 - \frac{1}{g(2k)q^{2k}} \right] \\
 &= \left(1 - \frac{1}{g(2)q^2} \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{g(4)q^4} \right) \cdots \left(1 - \frac{1}{g(2v)q^{2v}} \right) \\
 &= \frac{(g(2)q^2 - 1)(g(4)q^4 - 1) \cdots (g(2v)q^{2v} - 1)}{g(2)q^2 g(4)q^4 \cdots g(2v)q^{2v}} \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^v (1 - g(2)q^2)(1 - g(4)q^4) \cdots (1 - g(2v)q^{2v})}{q^{v(v+1)} \prod_{k=1}^v g(2k)} \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^v \prod_{k=1}^v (1 - g(2k)q^{2k})}{q^{v(v+1)} \prod_{k=1}^v g(2k)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore u_{e,v} \left(\frac{1}{g}; \frac{1}{q} \right) = \frac{(-1)^v u_{e,v}(g; q)}{q^{v(v+1)} \prod_{k=1}^v g(2k)}$$

$$\text{Hence, } \frac{1}{u_{e,v}(g; q)} = \frac{(-1)^v}{q^{v(v+1)} u_{e,v} \left(\frac{1}{g}; \frac{1}{q} \right) \prod_{k=1}^v g(2k)}$$

Using the above equation in Theorem 3.1 (ii), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} &= 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^v q^{2v} g(2v)}{q^{v(v+1)} u_{e,n} \left(\frac{1}{g}; \frac{1}{q} \right) \prod_{k=1}^v g(2k)} \\
 &= 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^v q^{-v(v-1)}}{u_{e,v} \left(\frac{1}{g}; \frac{1}{q} \right) \prod_{k=1}^{v-1} g(2k)}
 \end{aligned}$$

(v) From Theorem 3.1 (ii) and Theorem 3.1 (iii), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} &= 1 + \frac{T}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} \\ &= 1 + \frac{T}{1 - u_{e,\infty}(g; q) \Lambda} \\ &= 1 + \frac{T}{1 - \frac{\Lambda}{\frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)}}} \\ &= 1 + \frac{T}{1 - \frac{\Lambda}{1 + \frac{T}{1 - \frac{\Lambda}{1 + \dots}}}} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.2. If the product $u_{e,\infty}(g; q) = \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v)q^{2v})$ converges, then there are other equivalent forms of it, viz.

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad u_{e,\infty}(g; q) &= \sum_{\mu \in P^e} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) \\ (ii) \quad u_{e,\infty}(g; q) &= 1 - T \\ (iii) \quad u_{e,\infty}(g; q) &= 1 - u_{e,\infty}(g; q) \Lambda \\ (iv) \quad u_{e,\infty}(g; q) &= 1 - \frac{\Lambda}{1 + \frac{T}{1 - \frac{\Lambda}{1 + \dots}}} \end{aligned}$$

where P^e , Λ and T are exactly as in Theorem 3.1.

Proof (i) Consider

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{\mu \in P^e} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) \\ &= 1 + (-1)q^2g(2) + (-1)q^4g(4) \\ &+ (-1)q^6g(6) + q^6f(4)g(2) \\ &+ (-1)q^8g(8) + q^8g(6)f(2) \\ &+ (-1)q^{10}g(10) + q^{10}g(8)g(2) + q^{10}g(6)g(4) + \dots \end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } u_{e,\infty}(g; q) &= \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v)q^{2v}) \\ &= (1 - g(2)q^2) \cdot (1 - g(4)q^4) \cdot (1 - g(6)q^6) \\ &\cdot (1 - g(8)q^8) \cdot (1 - g(10)q^{10}) \dots \\ &= 1 + (-1)q^2g(2) + (-1)q^4g(4) + (-1)q^6g(6) + q^6g(4)g(2) \\ &+ (-1)q^8g(8) + q^8g(6)g(2) + (-1)q^{10}g(10) \\ &+ q^{10}g(8)g(2) + q^{10}g(6)g(4) + \dots \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

From (3.4) and (3.5), we obtain Theorem 3.2 (i).

$$\begin{aligned}
 (ii) \quad u_{e,\infty}(g; q) &= u_{e,0}(g; q) + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} (u_{e,2v}(g; q) - u_{e,2v-2}(g; q)) \\
 &= 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \left[\prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v)q^{2v}) - \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v-2)q^{2v-2}) \right] \\
 &= 1 + \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \left[\prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v-2)q^{2v-2}) (1 - g(2v)q^{2v} - 1) \right] \\
 &= 1 - \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} q^{2v} g(2v) u_{e,2v-2}(g; q) \\
 &= 1 - T \quad \text{where } T = \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} q^{2v} g(2v) u_{e,2v-2}(g; q)
 \end{aligned}$$

(iii) From Theorem 3.1 (ii), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)} &= 1 + \Lambda \quad \text{where } \Lambda = \sum_{v=1}^{\infty} \frac{q^{2v} g(2v)}{u_{e,2v}(g; q)} \\
 \implies u_{e,\infty}(g; q) &= 1 - u_{e,\infty}(g; q) \Lambda
 \end{aligned}$$

(iv) From the above result, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{e,\infty}(g; q) &= 1 - u_{e,\infty}(g; q) \Lambda \\
 &= 1 - \frac{\Lambda}{\frac{1}{u_{e,\infty}(g; q)}} \\
 &= 1 - \frac{\Lambda}{1 + \frac{T}{1-\Lambda}}
 \end{aligned}$$

where Λ, T are exactly as in Theorem 3.1.

4. SUMS OVER PARTITIONS INTO ODD DISTINCT PARTS, 1 AS ONLY PART, AND $v = v$ AS PART

In this section we prove the theorems taking sum over partitions as odd distinct parts, 1 as only part, and $v = v$ as part.

Theorem 4.1. *If the product $u_{o,\infty}(g; q) = \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v-1)q^{2v-1})$ converges, then it can be expressed in the following equivalent form*

$$u_{o,\infty}(g; q) = \sum_{\mu \in P^o} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) \tag{4.1}$$

where P^o is the set of partitions into odd distinct parts.

Proof Let P^o be the set of partitions into odd distinct parts. Since $l(\emptyset) = 0$, $n_{\emptyset} = 1$ and considering the odd distinct parts of partitions, we observe that

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &= 1, & 3 &= 3, & 4 &= 3 + 1, & 5 &= 5, & 6 &= 5 + 1, \\
 7 &= 7, & 8 &= 5 + 3, & 7 + 1, & 9 &= 9, & 5 + 3 + 1, & \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

Consider

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\mu \in P^o} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) &= 1 + (-1)q^1 g(1) + (-1)q^3 g(3) + (-1)^2 q^4 g(1)g(3) \\ &\quad + (-1)q^5 g(5) + (-1)^2 q^6 g(5)g(1) + (-1)q^7 g(7) \\ &\quad + (-1)^2 q^8 g(5)g(3) + (-1)^2 q^8 g(7)g(1) \\ &\quad + (-1)q^9 g(9) + (-1)^3 q^9 g(5)g(3)g(1) + \dots \tag{4.2} \\ &= 1 - q^1 f(1) - q^3 g(3) + q^4 g(1)g(3) \\ &\quad - q^5 g(5) + q^6 g(5)g(1) - q^7 g(7) \\ &\quad + q^8 [g(5)g(3) + g(7)g(1)] \\ &\quad - q^9 [g(9) + g(5)g(3)g(1)] + \dots \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} u_{o,\infty}(g; q) &= \prod_{v=1}^{\infty} (1 - g(2v-1)q^{2v-1}) \\ &= (1 - g(1)q^1)(1 - g(3)q^3)(1 - g(5)q^5) \\ &\quad (1 - g(7)q^7)(1 - g(9)q^9) \dots \tag{4.3} \\ &= 1 - q^1 g(1) - q^3 g(3) + q^4 g(1)g(3) - q^5 f(5) + \\ &\quad q^6 g(5)g(1) - q^7 g(7) + q^8 [g(5)g(3) + (g(7)g(1))] - \\ &\quad q^9 [g(9) + g(5)g(3)g(1)] \dots \end{aligned}$$

From (4.2) and (4.3), we obtain (4.1).

Theorem 4.2. *If P^1 be the set of partitions such that all parts are 1 only, then*

$$\sum_{\mu \in P^1} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) = (1 + qg(1))^{-1} \quad \text{where } |qg(1)| < 1.$$

If $g(1) = 1$, we get

$$\sum_{\mu \in P^1} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} = (1 + q)^{-1}$$

Proof Conventionally, $l(\emptyset) = 0$, $|\emptyset| = 0$. Since

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &= 1, \\ 2 &= 1 + 1, \\ 3 &= 1 + 1 + 1, \\ 4 &= 1 + 1 + 1 + 1, \dots, \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{so } l(1) = 1, l(2) = 2, l(3) = 3, l(4) = 4, \dots$$

$$\text{and } |1| = 1, |2| = 2, |3| = 3, |4| = 4, \dots$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\mu \in P^1} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) &= 1 + (-1)qg(1) + (-1)^2 q^2 g(1)g(1) \\ &\quad + (-1)^3 q^3 g(1)g(1)g(1) + \dots \\ &= 1 - q g(1) + q^2 (g(1))^2 - q^3 (g(1))^3 + \dots \\ &= (1 + qg(1))^{-1} \quad \text{where } |qg(1)| < 1. \end{aligned}$$

Taking $g(1) = 1$, we get

$$\sum_{\mu \in P^1} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} = (1 + q)^{-1}.$$

Theorem 4.3. If P^v be the set of partitions such that $v = v$, then

$$\sum_{\mu \in P^v} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) = 1 - \sum_{v \geq 1} q^v g(v).$$

If $g(v) = -1$, then

$$\sum_{\mu \in P^v} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) = (1 - q)^{-1}.$$

Proof Here $l(\mu) = 1$ for all $v \in \mathbb{N}$ and $|\mu| = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

$$\sum_{\mu \in P^v} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) = 1 - [qg(1) + q^2g(2) + q^3g(3) + \dots]$$

$$= 1 - \sum_{v \geq 1} q^v g(v).$$

If $g(v) = -1$, then

$$\sum_{\mu \in P^v} (-1)^{l(\mu)} q^{|\mu|} \prod_{\mu_i \in \mu} g(\mu_i) = (1 - q)^{-1}.$$

5. CONCLUSION

Here we presented interesting results for the sum over partitions as even distinct parts, odd distinct parts, 1 as only part and $v = v$ as part. At last, we conclude that if one consider the sums of the form $\sum_{\mu} g(\mu)$ over different partitions, then some more patterns may be obtained.

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